

The insects damaged the stem below the ground by nibbling, leaving the attacked parts fibrous. The leaves withered and turned brown. The beetles then moved below the soil surface, leaving behind a raised track and damaging other seedlings.

The extent of damage varied among the varieties (see table). Many of the experimental fields had to be resown.

Dieldrex 20 and Agroicide 26 DP applied at 0.085 and 0.25%, respectively, suppressed the infestation.

Effects of root-dip pesticide treatments on root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne graminicola*

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Surveillance profile for pest management

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A surveillance profile for pest management consists of a series of circles and squares that are connected to surveillance dates ($T_1, T_2 - - T_n$). The circle indicates "action needed," and the square, "action not needed" (see figure).

The use of this simple method begins shortly after planting the crop. To make decisions on "action needed" and "action not needed," the economic threshold level for the pest should first be known. Sampling stations or plots are then staked out at representative parts of the field. Surveillance is carried out at each station

by examining a specified number of randomly selected plants. If the pest population on the plant exceeds or approaches the established threshold level on a surveillance date, a circle is checked. If it is below the threshold level, a square is checked. This procedure is carried out for each surveillance date and for each plot throughout the surveillance period.

The surveillance profile gives growers and pest management specialists a visual running account of the pest severity on a crop. The effects of insecticide treatments, cultural practices, and, in certain instances, weather changes can be evaluated. A detailed description of the surveillance profile will be published in a forthcoming issue of the FAO Plant Protection Bulletin.

Preinoculation and postinoculation root-dip treatments were tested to compare the effectiveness of insecticides and nematicides in controlling and preventing larval invasion of the nematode *M. graminicola* under upland conditions. Each chemical was used at rates of 0, 25, 50, 100, and 200 ppm.

In the postinoculation treatments, infective larvae of the nematode were first allowed to invade the roots. Dipping roots in oxamyl at 200 ppm for 12 h reduced the number of surviving endoparasites as effectively as dipping them in the same chemical at 100 ppm for 24 h. Both fensulfothion at 50 ppm for 12 or 24 h and phorate for 24 h were as effective as oxamyl at 100 ppm for 24 h.

In the preinoculation root dip, oxamyl and fensulfothion were more effective at 100 and 200 ppm and superior to phorate or DBCP. Postinoculation root-dip treatments with oxamyl or fensulfothion for 24 h were as effective as preinoculation treatments for 12 h. The order of effectiveness of the chemicals was oxamyl or fensulfothion > phorate > DBCP. Fensulfothion and oxamyl retained toxicity for 15 days after root dipping; phorate, for 10 days; and DBCP, for 5 days. Systemic chemicals such as oxamyl, phorate, or fensulfothion persisted longer in plants when used as root dip.

A surveillance chart for recording decisions on pest management. University of Hawaii, Honolulu, Hawaii, USA.

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